

MILITARY WOMAN - METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION

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Annotation: The article talks about the relevance of the activities of women military personnel. The need for knowledge of communicative literacy in conducting preventive conversations and meetings with the population is analyzed.

Keywords and phrases: gender equality, female military personnel, military structure, communication, women's service, and equal rights.

Аннотация: В статье рассказывается об актуальности деятельности женщин-военнослужащих. Анализируется необходимость знания коммуникативной грамотности в проведении профилактических бесед и встреч с населением.

Ключевые слова и словосочетания: гендерное равенство, женщина-военнослужащая, военная структура, коммуникативность, служба женщин, равные права.

For the first time in 2019, on April 10, the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan announced the recruitment of women and girls for active military service. The increase in the number of women in camouflage is a sign of the modernization of the army in society. Today, military service is available to women in many countries of the world. The number of female military personnel is increasing all over the world. For example, about forty thousand women wear shoulder straps in the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation; four thousand women serve in military positions in the Republic of Belarus; eight thousand women serve in the troops of the Republic of Kazakhstan; more than a third of the national armed forces of the Kyrgyz army are women; Norway is a country where girls serve in the army on a mandatory basis for 12 months (the law was adopted in 2014); girls at the age of 18 are also conscripted into the Israeli army and serve for 24 months; in the US army, women are allowed to replace more than 90 percent of military positions, about two hundred thousand American women wear uniforms; in the British armed forces, women have the right to hold any position.

Traditionally, women are characterized by increased responsibility, lack of bad habits, and strive to endure the hardships of military service on an equal basis with men. This practice fully complies with international standards and realities.

As a rule, the requirements that are imposed on a person's professional speech in any sphere of his public activity are quite high and they are especially high if this sphere is inextricably linked with such concepts as military legal protection and law enforcement. [22]

To date, Uzbekistan is intensively heading into the world educational space and sets new goals for its youth. [7]

Professional communication of military personnel is conditioned by a wide range of socio-cultural spheres. [9]

In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen an increase in the number of women holding high positions in government bodies, which is an important step towards achieving gender equality. The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan clearly forms the principles of non-discrimination and equal rights for women and men. This is indicated by article 18 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which reads as follows: "All citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law without distinction of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, beliefs, personal and social status. Benefits can only be established by law and must comply with the principles of social justice." [1]

The legislation also establishes equal access of women and men to competitions for public service positions, we can see this principle in article 17 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men". [2]

Therefore, we understand that ensuring gender equality and eliminating gender discrimination are priorities of our State policy. After all, the true progress of society and the state is possible only if the rights and freedoms of every citizen are respected and respected, regardless of gender, race and other characteristics. The Decree of the President of our country "On measures to further accelerate the work on systemic support for families and women" highlighted the role of women in public administration. President of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev pronounced the iconic words "At least one deputy head in all state bodies and institutions of Uzbekistan will be a woman by 2024", which directly means the importance of women and strengthening their role in public and state life.

In order to ensure the effectiveness of activities to increase the socio-political activity of women, the full realization of their rights and interests, comprehensive support for motherhood and childhood, according to the decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 14, 2019, the posts of inspectors on working with women were introduced in the system of republican, regional, district (city) internal affairs bodies, where tasks are assigned to implement measures aimed at protecting the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of women, the provision, together with the relevant ministries and departments, of assistance to every woman in a difficult life situation, the prevention of offenses among them.

The socio-psychological characteristics of women make them indispensable, especially in services such as the service for the prevention of Crimes among women and minors. After all, who but a woman is able to understand a child, take over the pain of women and help them resolve their internal and external conflicts. And it is much easier for women in the role of a serviceman to cope, because it is often women who are supporters of peaceful conversation and conflict resolution with the help of communication skills. The main task of female military personnel in juvenile affairs is to hold meetings with the population, conduct conversations in schools, lyceums, boarding schools and universities. Female servicemen should be able to periodically professionally and qualitatively inform the population about the prevention of crimes and offenses through the mass media.

I would like female servicemen to be able to quickly argue their actions when performing any tasks, to have the skills to solve incidents of various types, which is necessary when solving tasks of increased difficulty. [10]

The variety of social situations in which female servicemen have to act outside the box determines the requirements for their communicative readiness, the ability to quickly enter into the essence of the event that took place and to positively solve this situation with their professional communication skills. Based on the above, it seems an urgent task to study the conscious choice of women's special professional activities in the military and law enforcement agencies. Working with victims of offenses, with teenagers assumed special sensitivity — and eventually became a "female" sphere. But dangerous "street" activities are mainly "male" spheres.

Therefore, we can understand that women are able to fully function as keepers of the hearth, and in the role of a successful military officer. Experts also

note that in the presence of female military personnel, male employees have an increase in male traits in an effort to distinguish themselves from them. At the same time, female servicemen also have a need to prove their indispensability to male servicemen, which is associated, among other things, with the superiority of men in physical strength. This gives them motivation to constantly work on themselves.

Therefore, we understand that their role in society, their huge contribution to the achievements of our Uzbekistan cannot be compared with anything.

Today, it is impossible to imagine any sphere of state and public activity without the participation of women. The President and the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan have made efforts to ensure equal access of women to public service. Due to this, despite the above-mentioned stereotypes, customs and foundations of Uzbek society that still exist today, women occupy high positions in all spheres of society and the state.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992
2. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 02.09.2019 No. ZRU-562
3. Akhmedova, H. and Khalikova, A. 2022. Speech culture of behavior is a significant professional duty of every inspector of crime prevention. Society and innovation. 3, 2/S (Apr. 2022), 239-245. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol3-iss2-pp239-245>
4. AKHMEDOVA H. O. Terminological system-a landmark model in the field of knowledge //YOUNG SCIENTIST Founders: LLC"Publishing House Young Scientist". – 2022. – No. 1. – pp. 264-266.
5. Akhmedova Khulkar, Dildora Khashimova, & Nasiba Niyazova. (2022). ON THE BASIS OF AN INTEGRATED COURSE, TEACHING PROFESSIONALLY ORIENTED FOREIGN LANGUAGE VOCABULARY TO STUDENTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC SPECIALITIES. ASEAN Journal on Science & Technology for Development, 39(4), 237–241. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7030819>
6. Akhmedova, H. O. Game technologies — qualitative growth of academic performance /Young scientist. — 2022. — № 14 (409). — Pp. 291-293. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/409/90033/>
7. Abdullayeva F., Akhmedova H. "Can the culture of speech of a crime prevention officer become his business card in society?" Journal //Science and Education. – 2021. – Vol. 2. – No. 7. – pp. 318-324.

8. Akhmedova H. O. Professionally-oriented language training for law enforcement officers -competitiveness and professionalism of the future //A young scientist. – 2020. – No. 32. – pp. 143-144.
9. Akhmedova, H. O. The development of language skills in the formation of a culture of communication of law enforcement officers / Young scientist. — 2021. — № 5 (347). — PP. 144-146. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/347/78011/>
10. Akhmedova, H. O. Terminological features of legal texts / H. O. // Young scientist. — 2022. — № 1 (396). — PP. 266-268. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/396/87542/>
11. Akhmedova, H. 2022. The use of interactive methods in the formation of communication skills of future prevention inspectors. Society and innovation. 3, 5/S (Jul. 2022), 30-34. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol3-iss5/S-pp30-34> .
12. Akhmedova H.O. "Mastering professional terminology with the help of an interactive way of learning" Society and innovations. – 2021. – Vol. 2. – No. 3. – pp. 114-119. <https://inscience.uz/index.php/socinov/index>
13. Akhmedova H. O. The narrowness of communication and ignorance of professional terms-the reason for the failure of students //A young scientist. – 2020. – No. 7. – pp. 234-236.
14. Akhmedova H. O. The need for law students of national groups to professionally-oriented training in Russian //Colloquium-journal. - Goloprstan Regional Employment Center, 2020. – No. 31-3. – pp. 43-45.
15. Akhmedovna, A.M., Olimjonovna, A. K., & Khamidovna, D. K. (2020).Enhancing student's writing through pre-writing activities. European Journal of Molecular and Clinical Medicine, 7(2), 3118-3130.
16. Akhmedova H. O. Online training-timeliness, economy, security, accessibility //A young scientist. – 2020. – №. 24. – pp. 394-395.
17. Vorontsova, Yu. A. Russian language for lawyers (practical course): textbook / manual /Yu. A. Vorontsova, E. Y. Khoroshko. – Belgorod, 2012. – 176 p.
18. Galizina E.G. Formation of general cultural linguistic competence in teaching professional vocabulary to students of the specialty "Jurisprudence": collection of scientific papers / E.G.Galizina // Language and communication in a modern multicultural society. – M., 2014.
19. Zvereva E.B. "Formation of communicative skills of future lawyers in the process of teaching the discipline "Russian language and culture of speech" (VUI FSIN of Russia) Russia, Vladimir DOI: [10.24411/2520-6990-2019-10786](https://doi.org/10.24411/2520-6990-2019-10786)

20. Karavaev, A.F. Psychological and pedagogical foundations of professional formation of specialists – employees of internal affairs bodies [Text] : method. manual / A. F. Karavaev. – M. : TSOKR of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia, 2005. – C. 227.
21. LolaYunusovna Akramova, Khulkar Olimzhonovna Akhmedova, Feruza Khashimova. (2020). THE PROBLEMS OF DISTANCE EDUCATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE PANDEMIC. PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt / Egyptology, 17(7), 8577-8583. Retrieved from <https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/3642>
22. Khalikova, A., Umbetaliev, A. and Akhmedova, H. 2022. The culture of speech is a fundamental priority in the activities of prevention inspectors. Society and innovation. 3, 4/S (May 2022), 84-90. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol3-iss4/S-pp84-90.24>.

